

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIALS

Glossary of ML Terminology

Term	Definition/Explanation
Machine Learning (ML)	A broad set of methods or tools comprised of self-improving algorithms for manipulating data. Supervised machine learning techniques use inputs and labels to train models for prediction or classification tasks, while unsupervised machine learning techniques use only input data, often for clustering or dimensionality reduction purposes.
Artificial Neural Net (ANN)	A popular category of machine learning models that take inspiration from the neurons of a brain. Inputs are propagated through the layers of the network to produce an output that represents abstract relationships within the input data. Each layer is comprised of nodes that perform operations to transform the data; collectively, these operations can approximate any smooth function if there are a sufficient number of layers.
Weights	The weights of a neural net define the multiplicative operation performed by its inputs. A value passed from one node to the next is multiplied by the weight of the connection before a bias may be added and the activation function is applied.
Biases	The biases of a neural net are the additive values used to transform inputs in each layer but are not as ubiquitous as weights. When biases are in use, they are typically added to the values in a layer after the input has been multiplied by the corresponding weight value and before the sum is passed through an activation function.
Parameters	The parameters collectively refer to the weights and biases of a neural net. Most parameters are learnable and will change as the model is trained.
Gradient	The gradient is taken with respect to a loss function and approximates the direction in the loss landscape that has the most rapid decrease. The model is updated using the gradient and a learning rate to approach a local or global loss minimum. In conventional training, the change in model parameters from one update to the next will be proportional to the learning rate, so the change in parameters is sometimes referred to as the gradient.
Activation Function	The activation function of a layer is used to add non-linear dynamics to the operations performed by a neural net. When an input is propagated through the net, it is modified using the weights and optional biases, then is passed through the activation function before it interacts with the parameters of the next layer. It is common to use the rectified linear unit (ReLU) function (negative inputs lead to an output of 0 and positive inputs are unchanged) for

	intermediate (hidden) layers and a sigmoid or softmax function for the final layer in classification models.
Deep Learning (DL)	Deep learning is a subfield of machine learning focusing on neural nets and related model architectures that use multiple hidden layers to approximate complex functions. In colloquial use, DL often carries a connotation that it is a more cutting-edge type of ML.
Convolutional Neural Net (CNN)	A popular model architecture for image classification tasks that uses convolutions to abstract spatial or temporal relationships within inputs. A CNN has weights and biases like simpler ANNs, but weights are convolved over inputs rather than multiplied with inputs. The weights of a CNN are also referred to as a filter or kernel – typically, a kernel operates over only one depth dimension (e.g., the red channel of an RGB image) and a filter refers to the stack of kernels for all depth channels of the input (e.g., an image filter could be comprised of three kernels corresponding to the red, green, and blue channels of the input). As the input is passed to later layers, the stacking of channels output by convolutional operations allows for filters to learn increasingly complex relationships within the input.
Loss Function	The loss function is used in supervised machine learning techniques to determine how far off model outputs are from the true or expected values so the model can be improved. Entropy or mean-squared error are examples of popular loss functions. At a high level, the loss function measures points on a loss landscape and gradient descent is used to iteratively adjust model parameters to move down the landscape in the steepest direction so as to minimize loss.
Backpropagation	When a neural net is training, error is estimated with a loss function and then used to determine the gradient of the loss with respect to the parameters of the net so they can be updated in the next iteration. The gradient of the loss is calculated through the backpropagation of error, essentially by computing partial derivatives of the loss starting at the last layer and moving backward to the first layer.
Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD)	Stochastic gradient descent is a popular optimization algorithm for training neural nets and other classification or regression models. It increases efficiency over traditional gradient descent by randomly selecting one instance to compute the gradient of the loss function and using this to update parameters, rather than computing every gradient in every iteration. At a high level, this process samples points on the loss landscape to move the model towards a minimum, though many problems in machine learning cannot guarantee a global minimum will be reached.
Learning Rate	While a model is being trained, the parameters are iteratively updated to minimize the loss based on the gradient of the loss function. The learning rate is used to scale the gradient during each update, essentially defining how big of a step the model will take on the loss landscape in each iteration. Many

advanced optimization techniques leverage dynamic learning rates that use additional features like momentum to determine the size of the update.

Supplementary Table 1: Expanded version of TABLE 1, depicting an overview of the Benefits and Opportunities vs. Drawbacks and Challenges associated with using FL to facilitate biomedical research collaborations among small institutions.

Benefits and Opportunities	Drawbacks and Challenges
<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Private data are never shared and access is revocable● Avoid reduplication or transfer of datasets● Leverage existing policies and infrastructure for data storage, access, and use● Distribute the burden of training across multiple parties, highly scalable● Train on data gathered from a more diverse population, outside the cohorts usually used for DL model development● Build larger collective datasets for rare diseases or populations while minimizing additional exposure● Experimental settings and model design are subject to wider peer review before the study is carried out● Distributed datasets and expertise are more robust than centralized● Collaboration is well-motivated by the ethos of open science● Enabling small institutions to become stakeholders in ML-aided medicine can expand access to its benefits● Decrease potential for algorithmic or systemic bias by using multiple datasets for differing contexts● Experts in model development without access to data can train on data they do not possess	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Data must be recorded and stored systematically to ensure semantic harmonization● Real patient datasets are likely to be non-IID, which can slow model convergence and degrade performance● Increasing the number of people and devices used for training leads to a larger attack surface● Information leakage in shared model updates can still expose vulnerable data in some contexts● Implementing additional techniques to further protect data privacy come at the expense of model performance● Distributed training requires reliable and secure networking capabilities● Small research institutions may lack sufficient computational resources● Novelty of FL can make it difficult to find collaborators who understand the pros and cons● Any application of ML-aided medicine can still be subject to bias and limited interpretability● Data quality is difficult to assess without access to the data● Best practices for IRB education, data governance, and inter-institutional communication in FL are not established

PRIVACY AND SECURITY IN MACHINE LEARNING

As we have discussed previously, considerations of data privacy are central to FL and warrant extra attention in biomedical contexts due to the sensitive nature of health records. For this reason, it is necessary to provide a brief introduction to the terminology of privacy and security in ML applications. The classical framework for security in this domain is the CIA model: Confidentiality, Integrity, and Availability^{46,86}. Confidentiality and privacy are closely related concepts dealing with restricted access to information. The distinction between these two terms is not always specified in the literature – some authors use them interchangeably, some differentiate them based on the trust between system agents, and others use confidentiality to refer to the model or data and privacy to refer to the data source (i.e., an attack on data confidentiality would violate the privacy of patients)^{46,50,86}. With our focus on healthcare data, patient privacy is the pressing concern and as such we will not discuss confidentiality as a separate concept. For a system to maintain its integrity, the model should produce accurate and reliable results. Biased results or attacks to manipulate model predictions are examples of how an ML system may lack integrity. Availability refers to the system’s ability to remain functional for legitimate users; availability is compromised if the system is not accessible, does not have usable performance (e.g., high latency), or produces low-quality outputs. The goals of the adversary are sometimes used to distinguish attacks on integrity (e.g., target the model to predict all instances of class A as belonging to class B) from attacks on availability (e.g., target the model to degrade accuracy across all inputs and classes)⁸⁶. For a general background on the security and privacy of machine learning, we refer the reader to ⁸⁶; for recent reviews of the security and privacy of FL, see ^{46,47}.

Supplementary Table 2: A description of each component of the MOTOR framework, including example questions that could be included in a checklist developed by the WG as part of their AIRs.

Concept/Theme	Description	Example Questions to Consider
Members	Ensuring that the site has a project lead to coordinate with other centers, that people with the necessary authority to make decisions about the data and the study have been included in the <i>Working Group</i> , and making sure everyone knows their responsibilities and has abilities to match	Who is responsible for the flow of communication between our IRB and those of our collaborators?
		Who has the authority to change firewall rules to let us connect to an aggregation server from our computing systems?
		If we encounter a problem with X, whose job will it be to fix it and how do we know they are able to do so?
Objectives	Reaching consensus on the objectives for the collaboration, ensuring these objectives are well-motivated, and setting up checkpoint goals to assess progress toward the objective	Are we all working on this for the same reason and can we agree on how we should measure progress?
		Why are we using FL instead of something else?
		Is our objective reasonable and desirable?
Technology	Verifying that there is an understanding of how FL works, how the specific	If we developed this technology, how will we train our collaborators to use it?

	technology to be implemented works, and validating this technology internally	If we did not develop this technology, who knows the code well enough to ensure it is not sharing private data?
		Can we test the software on our own dataset before we enter an agreement with others?
Obstacles	Assessing the obstacles that will need to be overcome at this specific site to fulfill their commitments to the project, developing an action plan to overcome these obstacles, and preparing to communicate this plan with people in relevant roles at the external groups	Why couldn't we do a full-scale multicenter study right now? In what order should we be addressing the problems that lay in our way? What challenges will be hardest to overcome or could create bottlenecks that prevent us from advancing in other areas?
Resources	Understanding the computational infrastructure, funding, skills, and data that the site has access to and determining how these resources can be leveraged to address challenges	Do we have access to a sufficient computer to train the model? Are we prepared to fix issues in the code or networking on the fly as they arise? Do we have research assistants that can help with this and are we able to fund them?

Supplementary Table 3: Description of components and example considerations for a data governance plan.

Concept/Theme	Description	Example Questions to Consider
Data Definitions	A set of precise shared standards across institutions that dictate what types of data will be used for training, how these data are encoded, and where these data come from	Do the procedures for recording and storing clinical observations differ from one institution to the next? Are there standard encoding systems for the attributes we will use? How did each institution select the data they will use and could this method lead to bias?
Accountability & Stewardship	Codified policies for ensuring that those charged with managing the data are able to do so, including procedures for dealing with data quality problems, standardized preprocessing, and educating all those involved on their rights and	How can we ensure that all participants are using good datasets and could audits be used to improve transparency? Who can make assurances that the participants whose

	responsibilities	data are used have consented?
		Who controls the aggregation server, will they have access to model updates, and how long will the models be stored?
Security	A shared understanding of the potential threats to the security of the FL system and a plan to ensure the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of data will not be violated ^{46,86}	How can existing intra-institutional authentication systems be leveraged to manage access and authorization?
		What methods can be used to verify the identity of stakeholders?
		Are datasets backed up locally and is there a risk that mismanagement could lead to data loss?
Privacy	A shared understanding of the potential threats to the privacy of the training data and a justification for the balance of privacy and utility that has been agreed upon	Should precautions such as differentially private model updates or restricted parameter sharing be used to limit information leakage?
		What is the worst-case scenario for patients whose data may be used?
		Are there any identifiable attributes in the training data and if so are they absolutely necessary to include?